

IMPROVING TECHNOLOGIES FOR SHAPING THE SOCIOLINGUISTIC COMPETENCE OF A1 LEVEL STUDENTS.

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Abstract: This classroom project aims at implementing and developing sociolinguistic and intercultural competences through the use of authentic materials for teaching A1 level learners in the English language classroom. The project departs from the idea that language is not isolated but integrated with culture, and the effort to change traditional practices for more meaningful ones. Thus, the communicative competence includes other aspects such as sociolinguistic and the intercultural competences which allow that learners use language in context and to become representatives of their cultures and be aware of other cultural identities.

Key words: technologies, sociolinguistic competence, english classroom, language classroom,

It is a tendency to use traditional approaches in language teaching, overlooking social and cultural components. The challenge is understood as an absence to include intercultural competences and it is evidenced in a lack of authenticity in the language classroom. The last creates a necessity to work in projects that motivate students to use language in context and to expose them to social and intercultural practices. Although the policies of bilingualism in a school keeps raising the standards, in most language classrooms there is a lack of spaces to include authentic language and intercultural practices. Therefore, there are many advantages about implementing fresher approaches in language teaching. The project was based on including a more complete design for learners to be exposed to social intercultural practices throughout the use of authentic materials. By including the use content methodologies and leaving aside the overuse of grammatical structures it is possible to expose learners to these competences.

In the theory, it is a detailed timeline which includes the most important definitions of the project. To start, Chomsky (1965) first coined terms such as 'competences' and 'performance' in the search to study linguistic issues. In the 1970's communicative methodologies and the 'communicative approach' were born (Campbell and Walles, 1970, Hymes, 1972). From those terms coined by the first academics a variety of terms were developed. For instance, the

‘sociolinguistic competence’ (Graham 1997, Meyerhof 2006), refers that language does not uniquely depend from grammatical abilities but from its use in certain contexts. In a more specific view, experts created the ‘intercultural competence’ a more narrow concept which goes further, and explains that a certain context is not enough, and that it is necessary to have the skills to interact in unknown contexts. Therefore, in this project, the intercultural competence became an effective platform to build sociolinguistic competences.

In this project there is an emphasis in the term ‘intercultural competence’ defined as the “ability to ensure a shared understanding by people of different social identities.” The term has to do with the ability to have a shared understanding of cultural beliefs, values and behaviors; also to recognize their own identity and culture, and to properly interact with others using the appropriate communicative skills. Some researchers explain that authentic materials are the best sources to teach intercultural practices; they are materials designed for social purposes. The inclusions of content based methodologies are also suggested with intercultural curriculums for language teaching and educational purposes. It is important to mention that at the end of the implementation there are four basic areas of reflection. Those areas are professional growth, students’ responses, linguistic outcomes and intercultural outcomes. The main instruments of reflection in this project are a personal journal notebook as a draft with the notes and the analysis of the teaching done or “On Action” by breaking down and interpreting the recalled information; for that journal, model of reflection was chosen. These reflections reveal the pertinence of the four areas in relation to the experts’ works, and the potential strengths and challenges of the project.

The inclusion of meaningful content related to real world issues and curriculum connections was pertinent to create lessons in which learners were able to create connections among language, content and intercultural knowledge; also, the assistance of the in-service teacher was key to develop the lesson plans and to work in discipline issues.

However, it was time consuming to design lessons and transform them in to the required activities which contained the necessary input. It was noticed that learners were highly motivated and that they were able to grasp and use language correctly without focusing on structure. Finally, it is important to include more strategies like pre-teaching vocabulary, modeling and the inclusion of activities that involve different learning styles.

In conclusion, the concept of 'intercultural competence' involves the idea that language is not isolated from, but a part of culture. The teaching of intercultural competences can create awareness and empathy towards other cultures and identity of the own culture. In our context, there is a necessity to work in the implementation of strategies for cross-cultural awareness in the classrooms. The project is based on students' needs to be skilled representatives of their own culture and learn how to interact better with other cultures and to widen their knowledge about the world. The vehicle selected was authentic materials and content added to the school's curriculum as a source of input to cultivate learners' communicative competence. The use of authentic materials concerns to this project since teaching 'real world' issues require actual records of social interaction. The use of constant reflection favored the improvement of the results which were mostly positive and consistent with the theoretical views. Students can be exposed to diverse stylistics varieties of language, different accents and other sociocultural characteristics of the language. In that sense, Mishan (2003) compares authentic materials as agents of socio-cultural facts. If the authentic materials are properly leveled to the activities, and strategies of pre-teaching vocabulary and modeling are used it is possible to obtain language profit. Respectively, the use of authentic materials and intercultural input is especially motivating for learners besides being a great source of cultural information.

Although Richards (2001) points out that authentic materials are difficult to understand, but instead it was noticed a great ability from students to grasp meaning from them.

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